

On “Bubble”-Modification of SIR Model

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In this article, we propose a modified model for the spread of SIR disease. The model is based on an assumption of the existence of two relatively separate groups, which are called bubbles. In the model we use, it is assumed that the rates of disease spread vary in both groups under consideration and between the groups too. A numerical experiment has been conducted for the proposed model.

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1. Introduction

Most of the epidemic spread models under consideration are based to some extent on the SIR model or its modifications [1–5].

Typically, models of this type focus on describing some average behavior and, accordingly, are deterministic. As a consequence, due to the random nature of the infection process, the models are not designed to take into account a variety of practical epidemic development scenarios and, accordingly, are poorly applicable to risk assessment tasks. In the article [6] we proposed a stochastic model, the main goal of which was to show how the random nature of events affects risk assessment.

But, the proposed model is oriented towards a relatively homogeneous epidemic spread environment with uniform parameters. In practice, due to various social, industrial and individual aspects, communication between individuals can form communities that are heterogeneous in the intensity of contacts, which we will call bubbles. As a result, the rate of spread of the disease in such communities may vary.

It should be noted that the idea of partial isolation of groups of individuals – bubbles arises naturally from simple practical assumptions about the need to reduce contacts. Such groups can arise both naturally (e.g., schools, businesses, urban areas, etc.) and administratively (e.g., in the form of a government-imposed quarantine). In particular, this idea was used to combat the spread of COVID-19 in New Zealand [7–9].

In this paper, we propose a stochastic model describing the spread of an epidemic in the case of two bubbles. The purpose of the work is not so much to build a prognosis of the development of the disease, but rather to assess the impact of randomness on the course of the disease on average.

Let us recall that the SIR model was originally developed in the works of Ross in 1916 [10], Ross and Hudson in 1917 [11, 12], Kermack and McKendrick in 1927 [13] and Kendall in 1956 [14] and has the form:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dS}{dt} &= -\frac{\beta IS}{N}, \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \frac{\beta IS}{N} - \gamma I, \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= \gamma I,\end{aligned}$$

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where N is the population size, $S \equiv S(t)$ denotes the number of susceptible individuals at time t , $I \equiv I(t)$ is the number of infected individuals and $R \equiv R(t)$ is the number of recovered individuals, β is the average number of contacts an individual has per unit of time, and the probability of an individual recovering over a time interval dt is γdt .

The model also assumes that:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} + \frac{dI}{dt} + \frac{dR}{dt} = 0,$$

$$S(t) + I(t) + R(t) = N = \text{const.}$$

The model solution was obtained by Miller (see [15, 16]):

$$\begin{aligned} S(t) &= S(0)e^{-\xi(t)}, \\ I(t) &= N - S(t) - R(t), \\ R(t) &= R(0) + \rho\xi(t), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\xi(t) = \frac{\beta}{N} \int_0^t I(\tau) d\tau, \quad \rho = \frac{\gamma N}{\beta}.$$

The model proposed in the paper [6] is based on the SIR model given above and takes into account the stochastic nature of the disease spread process under the assumption of discrete time $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ and has the form

$$\begin{aligned} DI_n &= S_{n-1}I_{n-1}\xi, \\ I_n &= I_{n-1} + DI_n - DI_{n-\mathcal{L}}, \\ S_n &= S_{n-1} - DI_n, \\ R_n &= R_{n-1} + DI_{n-\mathcal{L}}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

where I_n is the number of infected individuals at time n , S_n is the number of those who can become infected at time n , R_n is the number of immune individuals at time n , ξ is a normally distributed random variable describing the infectivity of susceptible individuals, with mean $E\xi = \beta$.

It should be noted that in the proposed model, since in the modeling we would like to take into account not only the number of contacts per unit of time, but also the probability of infection

upon contact, the coefficient β will be considered as the product of the average number of contacts per unit of time and the probability of infection upon a single contact between an infected and susceptible individual.

We believe that the variance for the quantity ξ can be reconstructed from experimental data. In the additional equation, DI_n denotes the increase in the number of infected at time n . We will also add an additional condition $DI_j = I_j = S_j = R_j = 0$ for $j < 0$.

2. Proposed SIR model modification

At this stage, we note once again that the model presented above is a formal description of the development of a disease within a certain community of individuals that is homogeneous in nature. However, when considering a real community, it is obvious that the interaction of community members is heterogeneous and this must be taken into account when conducting modeling. One approach is to use a contact matrix, the elements of which are the probabilities of infection upon contact between each specific pair of individuals. On the one hand, this approach, based on the use of a contact matrix, allows for the most detailed modeling of the course of the disease in the community, but on the other hand, it has a number of disadvantages.

Firstly, for real populations the dimension of the contact matrix is too large, which will affect the simulation time. Given the need to estimate some average behavior of the entire community as a whole, it will be necessary to conduct a large number of experiments in order to determine the contact matrix. We also note that this approach is imitative, that is, the state of the community will be assessed based on the state of each individual. This leads to additional requirements for the required computing power needed to carry out the simulation.

Secondly, when modeling a community comparable in size to real ones, difficulties arise

in assessing the probability of interaction between each specific pair of individuals, which means that researchers will have to make certain assumptions when forming the matrix and conduct a number of additional studies.

However, when considering this, a natural desire arises to identify relatively stable groups over time, which we will further call bubbles, the behavior within which is quite clearly defined. An example of such a group is a family. If the main principle of grouping is the territorial grouping of the population, then an urban area can be defined as a group, and if attention is paid to social activity, then, for example, a school or a work collective

When considering the bubble model, the previously mentioned models can be used to describe the dynamics of disease development within the bubble. This, in turn, will significantly reduce the size of the system that will be used for simulation. In fact, in modeling we will move from a contact matrix for all individuals in the community to a contact matrix of bubbles, the formalization of the values of whose elements, under a number of assumptions, can be significantly simpler.

In forming the bubble contact matrix at this stage of research, we propose the following approach: the probability of infection of an individual within a bubble is defined as the product of the probability of virus transmission upon contact and the probability of contact within the bubble. Here we assume that contacts within the bubble are equally probable. The likelihood of contact between blisters should be determined based on the measures taken to prevent the spread of the disease. For example, if a quarantine is introduced, this probability may be extremely low or even zero.

Based on the description of the models presented above, it follows that they cannot describe a situation where a population can be represented as two relatively isolated communities, since they lack the ability to regulate the rate of spread depending on the population. But the discrete model 1.1 can be

adapted to solve the problem.

Let us consider the case of two communities. For each of the communities, we introduce their own sizes N_1 and N_2 and coefficients β_1 and β_2 . To describe the infection process in cases of contact between communities, we will use the coefficient β_0 .

Then we modify the system (1.1) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} DI_{1,n} &= S_{1,n-1}I_{1,n-1}\xi_1 + S_{1,n-1}I_{2,n-1}\xi_0, \\ I_{1,n} &= I_{1,n-1} + DI_{1,n} - DI_{1,n-\mathcal{L}}, \\ S_{1,n} &= S_{1,n-1} - DI_{1,n}, \\ R_{1,n} &= R_{1,n-1} + DI_{1,n-\mathcal{L}}, \\ DI_{2,n} &= S_{2,n-1}I_{2,n-1}\xi_2 + S_{2,n-1}I_{1,n-1}\xi_0, \\ I_{2,n} &= I_{2,n-1} + DI_{2,n} - DI_{2,n-\mathcal{L}}, \\ S_{2,n} &= S_{2,n-1} - DI_{2,n}, \\ R_{2,n} &= R_{2,n-1} + DI_{2,n-\mathcal{L}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

Since the CIR model does not provide an opportunity to estimate fluctuations in the number of infected, it is difficult to use this model for assessing the required amount of resources in the case, when an infection developing according to a scenario worse than the predicted value. This means, that if we assume that the distribution of the number of infected is symmetric or close to symmetric, then the estimate based on the above solution will be correct for approximately 50% of all possible scenarios, that is unacceptable.

The variances of normally distributed random variables ξ_0 , ξ_1 and ξ_2 can be estimated from experimental data.

3. Numeric experiment

The following parameter values were used for the numerical experiment $N_1 = 400$, $N_2 = 600$, $\mathcal{L} = 14$, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.9$, $\beta_0 = 0.01$. Respectively $\xi_1 = \mathcal{N}(\frac{\beta_1}{N_1}, \frac{\beta_1}{2N_1})$, $\xi_2 = \mathcal{N}(\frac{\beta_2}{N_2}, \frac{\beta_2}{2N_2})$, $\xi_0 = \mathcal{N}(\frac{\beta_0}{N_1+N_2}, \frac{\beta_0}{2(N_1+N_2)})$ are normally distributed random variables.

We assume that initially there was only 1 infected person in the first group, and there were no infected people in the second group, i.e $I_{1,0} =$

1, $I_2, 0 = 0$. For all remaining equations of the system 2.1, we set the initial values to zero.

The numerical experiment was carried out using the Monte Carlo method with a total number of trajectories of 2000. The figure 1 shows

FIG. 1. (Color online) Temporal dependencies (discrete time n) of Expectations of the model 2.1. Red color refers to the number of infected, green refers to the number of recovered and the black one refers to the number of susceptible individuals. Solid lines are used for the whole population, dotted lines are used for the bubble of the size $N_1 = 400$, dashed ones are used for the bubble of the size $N_2 = 600$.

the mean values of the system state indicators, where the number of susceptibles is indicated in black, recovered in green, and infected in red. The vertical axis indicates the number of people, the horizontal axis indicates the number of days. The dotted lines correspond to the indicators of the first group; the dashed lines to the second, and the solid lines to the general state of the system.

The trajectory realizations shown in demonstrate the possible diverse dynamics of the disease course.

The presented implementations show that deviations from the average values can be quite significant, therefore, when predicting the development of a disease, it is necessary to take into account the distribution of the random process under study.

The figure 3 shows the standard deviation of the number of infected people on average for the population and for each of the groups,

FIG. 2. (Color online) Four realizations of the random process. Colors and lines styles are the same as for 2.1.

respectively.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Std. deviation upon discrete time n for the infected individuals.

When assessing risks, one should take into account the form of the deviation shown in the figure 3, since this form means that after reaching a certain peak in the spread of the disease, another peak may occur or the attenuation of the spread will be quite slow.

The figure 4 shows graphs of the average number of cases (in red) and some upper estimate of the dynamics, obtained as the sum of the mean value and the standard deviation (in blue). The

FIG. 4. (Color online) Dynamics (in discrete time) of the Expectations with std.deviation for infected individuals. The red line corresponds to the mean value of the infected individuals in whole population. The blue line corresponds to the sum of mean value and standard deviation of the infected.

information shown in the figure 4 may also be useful when assessing risks.

In particular, it should be noted that the peak of the disease may be higher and occur earlier than expected, since the peak on the blue graph is shifted to the left relative to the average number of infected.

4. Conclusion

An important aspect of modeling and subsequent forecasting is the presence of simplifications and inaccuracies in the description of a process, but also we need to create models that allow evaluating the values of functionals from the obtained solutions, which, we believe, is confirmed by researches (see, e.g. [17, 18]).

The proposed modification of the SIR model allows us to predict the dynamics of the epidemic, and also to calculate the parameters of a possible random course of the disease, expressed in the form of functionals along trajectories, which can be used in risk management.

In this paper, we show that the random nature of the process under study can lead to significant fluctuations and the deviation of the specific value of the number of infected people relative to the predicted one can be very significant (see. Fig. 4).

Such behavior cannot be described using deterministic models.

It should be noted that the parameters chosen for the modeling correspond to a very aggressive course of the epidemic, i.e., when there is a high probability that all individuals will be affected. But even in this case, deviations from the average value can be very significant (in the case under consideration, more than 100 people with a total population of 1000 people). This means that by relying on valuation methods such as moving averages, we significantly underestimate potential costs.

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